

Prune Belly Syndrome Associated with Congenital Right Bronchogenic Cyst in a Term Female Neonate in Calabar, Cross Rivers State, Southern Nigeria: A Case Report

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Abstract

Background: Prune Belly Syndrome (PBS), commonly found in males, is characterised by abdominal muscle aplasia/hypoplasia, urological abnormalities, and bilateral cryptorchidism. Pulmonary hypoplasia is the predominant pulmonary abnormality in PBS. Because of its rarity and loco-regional lack of data, we report a case of a term female neonate with prune belly syndrome and bronchogenic cysts.

Case presentation: A three-day-old female neonate of the Efik ethnic group in Nigeria presented with respiratory distress noticed 12 hours after birth. The child was noted to have a prune-like abdomen and diagnosed with PBS (category 3) and Bronchogenic cyst, making it an interesting clinical scenario. Unfortunately, the baby passed away on the 6th day of life due to respiratory compromise, 16 hours after undergoing cyst excision surgery.

Conclusion: Although pulmonary hypoplasia is the most commonly documented pulmonary abnormality (58%), limited data on pulmonary abnormalities in PBS hampers evidence-based documentation. Adopting a multidisciplinary approach in the management of patients with PBS is essential. Genetic counselling and family support are crucial in cases where there is no family history of genetic or congenital anomalies, such as the index case. Early diagnosis and close monitoring for potential complications are recommended for better outcomes.

Background

Prune belly syndrome (PBS), also known as Eagle-Barrett syndrome, is a rare multi-system condition characterised by deficient or absent abdominal wall

muscle, urinary tract anomalies and cryptorchidism.[1-4] The presentation of PBS is variable as concomitant non-genitourinary anomalies have been noted in 3 out of 4 patients with PBS, including cardiovascular (25%),

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Prune belly syndrome, Respiratory distress, Congenital anomaly, Congenital Bronchogenic Cyst.

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pulmonary (58%), gastrointestinal (24%) and musculoskeletal (22%) abnormalities.[3,4] Global incidence ranges from 1 in 30,000 - 40,000 live births, and about 3-5% of cases occur in females, implying an almost exclusivity to males (96%).[4-7]

Although prognosis varies and depends on the degree of renal involvement, PBS has a perinatal mortality rate of 10-25%. [3,6] Some authors have also reported a high in-hospital mortality of 31% and a high association of prematurity (43%) with attendant pulmonary complications requiring ventilator support. [5,6]

Congenital Bronchogenic Cyst (CBC) is the most prevalent primary cyst of the mediastinum, originating from the primitive foregut. [2,8] It is lined by respiratory-type epithelium and usually contains clear fluid; however, it can also contain air or blood. [9,10] The clinical presentation is variable, with symptoms ranging from respiratory distress at birth to late symptoms in later years. [9,11]

Although there is no consensus on the management of bronchogenic cysts, most clinicians advocate early removal, even in asymptomatic patients, as they can eventually threaten life by severe compression, infection, haemorrhage and rupture. [12-14]

Case Presentation

A full-term singleton pregnancy newborn baby was referred to the neonatology unit of the University of Calabar Teaching Hospital (UCTH) from the Nigerian Navy Reference Hospital (NNRH), Calabar. The baby was noticed to have difficulty breathing 12 hours after birth and an oxygen saturation of 68% at the onset of respiratory distress, which necessitated airway suctioning and supplemental oxygen therapy, improving the oxygen saturation to 82%.

Gestational age was at 41 weeks and birth was by spontaneous vaginal delivery. The APGAR scores were 6¹, 7⁵ and 9¹⁰. Birth weight was 3.1kg, birth length was 49cm, occipitofrontal circumference was 37cm and chest circumference was 37.5 cm.

The neonate was born to a 34-year-old Para 3 of the Efik ethnic group in Nigeria. Prenatal sonography was uneventful till about 30 weeks of gestation, when an ultrasound scan showed fluid in the foetal abdomen. A repeat ultrasound scan done at 40 weeks' gestation showed oligohydramnios, which necessitated the decision for induction of labour, however, labour occurred spontaneously. No prenatal intervention was done.

On admission, physical findings revealed respiratory distress (flaring alae nasi, subcostal recession and intercostal recession), tachypnoea (respiratory rate = 90 cycles per minute), bulging of the right hemithorax, hyper-resonant percussion note on the right hemithorax, reduced air entry in the right lung zone and bronchovesicular breath sounds. The liver was 3cm palpable below the costal margin; firm, not tender and

a prune-like abdominal skin was noted (Fig. 1). There were no other abnormal clinical findings and urine output was normal.

Figure 1. Clinical Picture of the Neonate Showing Prune-Like Abdominal Skin

A full blood count and serum electrolyte, urea and creatinine were normal findings.

Radiologic findings include bilateral mild pelvicalyceal dilation and thinned-out anterior abdominal wall muscles on ultrasound scan, a right-sided lucent lung lesion on chest radiograph (Figs 2 & 3), and a unilocular right lower lobe lung cyst measuring 3.74 x 4.06cm (transverse x anteroposterior) with air-fluid levels on a non-contrast computed tomography (CT) scan of the chest, other organs appeared normal (Fig4).

Figure 2: Chest Radiograph Showing a Right-Sided Thin-Walled, Oval-Shaped, Hyperlucent Lesion

A diagnosis of prune belly syndrome with a right congenital bronchogenic cyst was made. The neonate was treated with humidified oxygen therapy at 2L/min by nasal prongs, prophylactic antibiotic (IV ceftriaxone 100mg/kg/day) and intravenous fluid 10% dextrose at 60mls/kg/day via a soluset.

Figure 3: Right Lateral Chest Radiograph Showing Hyperlucent Circumscribed Lesion

Figure 4: Chest CT Radiograph Showing a Unilocular Cyst Lesion

On the fifth day of life, an elective right anterolateral thoracotomy for cyst excision under general anaesthesia was performed. The findings include a right lung cyst with mucinoid content measuring 10x8x6 cm between the right middle and lower lobes, compressing the right lower lung lobes (Figs 5 & 6). The cyst was excised and sent for histopathology.

Thoracotomy closure was done, and the child was transferred to the neonatal intensive care unit for elective mechanical ventilation. Histological analysis of the excised lung tissue revealed findings consistent with a diagnosis of a right bronchogenic cyst. Sadly, the child passed away 16 hours later, and post-mortem autopsy was deferred by the parents due to cultural beliefs.

Figure 5: Clinical Picture Showing Intra-op cyst Finding

Figure 6: Clinical Picture Showing Intra-op cyst Finding

Discussion and Results

Prune Belly Syndrome (PBS) is a rare congenital disorder characterised by a triad of symptoms, including deficient abdominal muscles, urinary tract abnormalities, and undescended testes in males.[4,15] Despite extensive research, the exact aetiology of PBS remains elusive, with multiple theories postulated.[3,15] The mesodermal defect theory has been proposed, but PBS is now widely recognised as a multifactorial condition, influenced by a complex interplay of genetic and environmental factors.[16] Although specific genetic involvement or consistent risk factors have not been established, ongoing research offers promising insights into the genetic underpinnings of this enigmatic syndrome. Classifying PBS poses challenges due to the significant variability in its presentation and severity. The widely used Woodard classification provides an overview, but

its limitations are evident in cases that do not fit neatly into the defined categories. [1,17] The Woodard Classification groups it into three categories [4]:

1. Category I (20%) is characterised by renal dysplasia, severe oligohydramnios, pulmonary hypoplasia and Potter's features.
2. Category II (40%): Typical triad features, moderate or unilateral renal dysplasia, no pulmonary hypoplasia, and may progress to renal failure.
3. Category III (40%): Incomplete or mild triad features, mild uropathy, no renal dysplasia, no pulmonary hypoplasia and normal renal function.

Recent studies have explored alternative approaches to classification, reflecting the need for a more comprehensive system to encompass the diversity of PBS manifestations. For instance, some researchers have proposed incorporating molecular genetic findings to refine the classification and identify distinct subtypes based on underlying genetic factors. [4,17,18] Genetic involvement in PBS remains an area of interest and debate. While some authors have reported potential genetic contributions, the genetic basis is yet to be fully explained. Notably, some cases, including our index case, do not exhibit the expected urinary tract findings and abdominal appearance in female patients, raising questions about sex-specific expression patterns and possible genetic modifiers. [4,7,15,17]

Beyond the classic triad of symptoms, PBS often presents with systemic involvement, affecting other organ systems in approximately 75% of patients.[15] Although pulmonary hypoplasia is the most commonly documented pulmonary abnormality (58%), limited data on pulmonary abnormalities in PBS hampers evidence-based documentation. Could the occurrence of CBC in PBS, as seen in the index case, be a coincidence or mutually inclusive? These are questions that beget answers as a good understanding of these associated health complications is crucial for comprehensive management and care coordination. [19,20]

The management of PBS requires a multidisciplinary approach, tailored to the individual patient's needs. A team of specialists, including paediatricians, urologists, nephrologists, and surgeons, collaborates to address the unique challenges PBS poses. Surgical interventions are often necessary to address urinary and abdominal issues, while early intervention can improve outcomes for associated health conditions.

In some African countries, including Nigeria, the death of a neonate or young person is often associated with certain cultural beliefs/myths, which are perceived as ominous signs. [21-24] Cultural beliefs, deeply ingrained in the fabric of societies, often determine how people perceive health and medical procedures. [23-25] This case subtly highlights the influence of cultural context, where parental decisions were shaped

by superstitious beliefs, leading to the deferment of post-mortem autopsy.

Conclusion

PBS remains a fascinating yet complex syndrome, challenging the medical community to unravel its enigmatic aetiology and genetic underpinnings fully. While classification systems continue to evolve, a comprehensive understanding of the clinical spectrum is essential for providing personalised and effective management. Further research and collaborative efforts hold the key to unravelling the mysteries of PBS and advancing patient care.

List of Abbreviations

1. PBS---Prune Belly Syndrome
2. CBC---Congenital Bronchogenic Cyst
3. UCTH--University of Calabar Teaching Hospital
4. NNRH--Nigerian Navy Reference Hospital
5. CT--Computed tomography

Declarations

Human Ethics and Consent to Participate Declarations: Not applicable.

Consent for publication: This manuscript represents an honest work; it has been read and approved by the aforementioned authors for review and subsequent publication by European Journal of Medical and Health Research. Also, written informed consent for the publication was obtained from the parents.

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Authors' contributions:

1. A.J.: data collection, literature search, manuscript editing
2. D.J.G: data collection, manuscript writing and editing
3. E.I.: Literature search, data collection, manuscript review
4. M.U.E.: data collection, manuscript review
5. S.O.O: Literature search, manuscript review
6. A.E.: definition of intellectual content, manuscript review
7. S.B.A: Literature search, manuscript editing

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